

ISic3617

I.Sicily inscription 3617

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Netum

Place of origin (modern)

near Noto

Provenance

chiesa rupestre di S. Marco nel casale Cardinale a Nord Ovest di Noto

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Noto, Chiesa rupestre di S. Marco nel casale Cardinale

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645690

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 58.1049.4

Rizzone, V.G. 2008. Vecchie e nuove, vere e presunte iscrizioni tardo-antiche della campagna Netina. *Nea Rhome*. 5: 17-26. At 20 fig.3

Orsi, P. 1898. Chiese bizantine nel territorio di Siracusa. *Byzantinische Zeitschrift*. 7: 1-28. At 14

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